

The Use of Substances and Sports Performance among Youth: Implications for Lagos State Sports

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Abstract—The focus of this study was to determine the factors associated with the use of substances for sport performance of youth in Lagos state sport. Questionnaire was the instrument used for the study. Descriptive research method was used. The estimated population for the study was 2000 sport men and women. The sample size was 200 respondents for purposive sampling techniques were used. The instrument was validated in its content and constructs value. The instrument was administered with the assistance of the coaches. Same 200 copies administered were returned. The data obtained was analysed using simple percentage and chi-square (χ^2) for stated hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings reveal that sport injuries exercise induced and anaphylaxis and asthma and feeling of loss of efficacy associated with alcohol used on sport performance among the users of substances. Alcohol users are recommended to partake in sport like swimming, basketball and volleyball because they have space of time for resting while at play. Government should be fully in charge of the health of sport men and women.

Keywords—Implications, Lagos state, substances, sports performance, youths.

I. INTRODUCTION

SPORT is an amusement or fun, an activity engaged in either outdoors or indoors, meant for enjoyment and exercise. These activities bring people together in one way or another enhanced better understanding [2]. Reference [10] states that sports involve physical exercise, with full stamina, skill and a display of healthy structural framework in correlation with the functioning capacity of the vital organs of the body. In addition, sports create atmosphere of a favourable contest between one and another in the area of entertainment, and pleasure which may likely geared towards award of laurels. As a result, individuals need a complete state of wellness, alertness, and physical fitness to excel.

Sports are considered to be natural part of life, whether it is engaged in for competitive or just play for fun and enjoyment, the opportunity to take part in any sporting activities according to [8], [9] should be basic human rights, however, sport is a household affair of every nation throughout the world. Nigeria is not an exception, in a sense that its influence cuts across all factors of our national life.

Sports supposedly prove and attest to healthy nature of the individual that determines the efficiency of his outcome in any event. Reference [10] also stated that individuals are involved in any keen competition depending on the healthy nature of the structures, organs of the body functioning anatomically as

it supposed to be determinant to the success of the individual in any participation event.

Impairment of the circulatory and central nervous system by the use of substances affects the normal physiology of the whole body systems which may result in poor physical performance. Substances are some materials with a particular texture or an intoxicating drink or drugs performance enhancing, [7] with the challenges athletes face now, we never can say who might be misusing a performance enhancing substance, so it's better to be prepared and armed with the right information before it happens.

Reference [9] states that typically, a substance or method is considered to performance enhancing when it has the potential to enhance, or enhances sports performance and when it represents an actual or potential health risk to an athlete but some athletes use the most harmful and abused substances.

He further stated the example of substances, Anabolic hormones, Beta-z Agonists, and Diuretics which expel water from body, and athletes who need to meet weight restrictions may be tempted to use them. The primary medical use of this compound is to treat conditions such as hypertension, kidney, and congestive heart failure. In addition, amphetamines, caffeine anaphylaxis, asthma, feeling of loss of efficacy are stimulants associated with alcohol use for performance enhancing which common among Lagos State athletes.

Alcohol is an example of a substance that act on the central nervous system when use with stimulant substance in other to stimulate the body and mind to perform at optimal levels by increasing focus, energy and aggression will only work for short time on long period of time it will become depressant by depress the athletes action. Moderate alcohol intake of 0.06, 0.10 g/d result in alcohol and motor skill alternation by slowing down reaction time, decreased hand, eye motion, decreased accuracy and balance impaired tracking, and visual search [12].

Alcohol does not improve vascular work capacity resulting in a decrease in overall performance levels, slow down exercise and sports. Running cycling times weakening of the pumping forces of the heart impaired temperature regulation during exercise decreased jump height and decreased 200 and 400 meters run performance, faster fatigue during high intensity exercise, [3]. Exercise an sport promote feelings of well being of individual, decreases depression, improve mental and psychological health by enhancing individuals psychedelic state of mind, aids sleep and increase the capacity of dealing with daily life events and the environment. Exercise and sports strengthening the athletics skill, the body, reduces the

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incidence of diabetes and obesity [6]. Exercise augments an individual's sex appeal linked with higher levels of self esteem, there are many awards merited from sport performance which include financial benefit, moral, emotional pride that boost individual ego of being a productive member of the society. Use of substances may impede these benefits. However, it is generally assumed that the use of substances either drugs or drinks is to improve strength and boost individual's abilities of excellent performance. The use of substance like alcohol demoralized integrity, loss of self esteem and it makes individual's not to realize their full potentials hence substance use if obstacle to social development [1].

Regular exercise and training with good nutrition increase sport performance. Reference [5] says, sport performance is associated with superiority of the mind and body coupled with good management of human and material resources. Barriers to sport performance can be seen in the following: fragile or low self-confidence, breakdown in trust, high expectation, fear of failure and social approval, perfectionism and so on. Physical and psychological factors can affect how an athlete feel and perform in his motor and sport skills. These factors can lead to sudden shift in performance level up or down and psychological dependence which athletes are try to user came by tempted to use alcohol or any drugs for performance enhancing, with the reasons that alcohol use might the prevent sports injuries and feeling of loss of efficacy will be overcome.

The use of alcohol is dangerous because it is associated with physical, psychological and psychedelic dependency. It gives feeling of loss of efficacy individual hardly excel to his optimal abilities there is redundancy continual feeling of unwillingness. "Reference [4] stated that heavy alcohol use lead to anaphylaxis and asthma during sport activities. Sport injuries are very common with alcohol than non alcoholic sportsman. There is loss of appetite decreasing individual stamina, unable to complete full time game and hardly perform 400 and 1500 meter race.

Reference [3] stated that alcohol replaces the normal macro nutrient intake (protein, carbohydrates and fats) and nutritional deficiency diseases can develop which lower muscles glycogen levels and normal aerobic energy production. Alcohol use has affected a good number of prospective sportsmen and reducing the number of possible champions as a result of poor performance.

Alcohol is the most common substance use among sportsmen and women in South East and South West of Nigeria especially Lagos State. Alcohol use has affected a good number of prospective Sportsmen and reducing the number of possible champions as a result of poor performance. As a result of these problems of alcohol use researcher decided to investigate effect of alcohol on sport performance. The focus of the study is to determine the effects of alcohol use on sports performance, especially if sports injury, exercise induced anaphylaxis and asthma, feeling of loss of efficacy from use of alcohol affect sports performance.

That is, what are those factors that are associated with alcohol use on sports performance in Lagos State.

A. Research Question

1. Does sports injury has association with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of the substances in Lagos State sports.
2. Does feeling of loss of efficacy associate with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of the substances in Lagos State sports.
3. Does exercise induced anaphylaxis and asthma associate with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of the substance in Lagos State sports.

B. Hypotheses

1. Sports injury will not significantly associate with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of the substances in Lagos State sports.
2. Feeling of loss of efficacy will not significantly associate with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of the substances in Lagos State sports.
3. Exercise induced anaphylaxis and asthma will not significantly associate with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of the substances in Lagos State sports.

C. Significance of the Study

The result will be beneficial to physical and health educating sports science generally, all arms of media will use the result provided in this study to educate the sportsmen and women. The study is delimited to sportsmen and women in some selected Local Government Area in Lagos State, restricted to the variable of the Study.

D. Methodology

Descriptive research survey was used for the study. The populations for this study were sportsmen and women in Lagos State sports. The sample for this study comprised of 200 respondents. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the number of respondents needed for the study. The instrument for the collective of data was self structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was in the four point score rating the modified Likert-type using strongly agree 4, agree 3, disagree 2, strongly disagree 1. The face and content validity of the research instrument were ascertained by the experts in the department of physical and health education and research consultant in the faculty of education. The completed questionnaire forms were thereafter sorted, coded, and analyzed with the use of percentage and chi-square to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

II. DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

- Hypothesis I: Sports injury will not significantly associate with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of the substances in Lagos State sports.

TABLE I
 RESULT OF CHI-SQUARE (χ^2) ANALYSIS ON SPORTS INJURY WITH ALCOHOL
 AND SPORTS PERFORMANCE

Response	Frequency	Percentage %	DF	Critical value	Calculated value
Strongly A	68	34	3	7.82	8.52
Agree	82	41			
Disagree	20	10			
Strongly D	30	15			
Total	200	100			

Table I shows that the calculated chi-square value of 8.52 was greater than chi-square table value of 7.82, with Df = 3 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that sports injury will not significantly associate with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of substance in Lagos State sport is hereby rejected, indicating that sports injury is associated with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of substance in Lagos State sports.

- Hypothesis II: Exercise induced anaphylaxis and asthma will not significantly associate with alcohol use on sport performance among the user of substance in Lagos State sports.

TABLE II
 RESULT OF CHI-SQUARE (χ^2) ANALYSIS ON EXERCISE INDUCED
 ANAPHYLAXIS ASTHMA

Response	Frequency	Percentage %	DF	Critical value	Calculated value
Strongly A	78	39	3	7.82	9.58
Agree	50	25			
Disagree	42	21			
Strongly D	30	15			
Total	200	100			

Table II shows that the calculated chi-square value of 9.58 was greater than chi-square table value of 7.82 with Df 3 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that exercise induced anaphylaxis and asthma will not significantly associate with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of substance in Lagos State sports was rejected, indicating that exercise induced anaphylaxis and asthma is associated with alcohol use on sport performance.

- Hypothesis III: Feeling of loss of efficacy will not significantly associate with alcohol use on sports performance among the user of substance in Lagos State sports.

TABLE III
 RESULT OF CHI-SQUARE (χ^2) ANALYSIS ON FEELING OF LOST OF EFFICACY
 AND SPORT PERFORMANCE

Response	Frequency	Percentage %	DF	Critical value	Calculated value
Strongly A	70	35	3	7.82	8.72
Agree	68	34			
Disagree	36	18			
Strongly D	26	13			
Total	200	100			

Table III shows that the calculated chi-square value of 8.73 was greater than chi-square table value of 7.82, with Df = 3 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which

states that feeling of loss of efficacy will not significantly associate with alcohol use on sport performance among the user of substance in Lagos State sport was rejected, indicating that feeling of loss of efficacy is associated with alcohol use on sport performance among the user of substance in Lagos State sports.

III. DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

The findings obtained from Table I shows that sports injury is associated more with individual who use alcohol on sports performance.

Alcohol reduces individual strength or stamina from obtaining the height of his performance. There is difficult acceleration and malfunctioning of the injured part leading to poor performance. This finding is in line with [11] that stated that people indulged alcohol consumption are prone to increased health risky during prolonged exercise in not environments. So therefore, sports injury was a significant factor of alcohol use on sports performance among the user of substance in Lagos State sports.

The result revealed from Table II shows that exercise induced anaphylaxis and asthma are associated with alcohol use and sport performance in Lagos State. Athletes who has been using substances like alcohol for long time, happen to experiencing asthmatic attack or bronchospasm and not be able to compete in prolong sports activities. This is in line with [4], exercise induced bronchospasm among healthy elite across country shown skier and non athletics student stated that regular exercise in cold, dry air is believed to be a predisposing factor for exercise induced bronchospasm.

The findings obtained from Table III shows that feeling of loss of efficacy is associated with alcohol use on sports performance, since athletes with alcohol use feels they lost sense of determination as a result refused pat taking in sports activities. This is in line with [13] which states that alcohol use on sport performances impair reaction time and mental acuity for up to several days after consumption. All this is of severe consequence to the athlete. Performance will be reduced and decrease in hand eye coordination will be impairing judgment due to loss of feelings of efficacy. Loss of feeling efficacy may be factors of using alcohol to some athletes, for such there must be prevention specialists efforts involve a mix of approaches delivered to individuals and team and recommend sports.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings from this study, it was obvious that alcohol use has negative influence on sports performance both psychological and physiological. Alcohol use aggregate asthmatic attack and cardiovascular disorder which affects individual physical activity hence expected performance from sports participant are not achieved. Alcohol remains one of the most abused drugs among athletes despite they well known negative effects it can have on the mind and body. It is essential for the athletes to understand how alcohol damage and how it destroy athletic ambitions.

V. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are suggested.

1. Government should take appropriate care of the athletes before and during competitions.
2. Athletes should endeavour to diagnose and ascertain their state of health so as to know the right game(s) suitable for their health.
3. Treatment and follow up of exercise regimen programmed for chronic alcohol user, should be monitored.
4. Use of alcohol may be detrimental to athletes but athletes who choose to drink the ACSM recommendations should followed that is pre event avoid alcohol beyond low amount social drink for 48 hours, post exercise rehydrate first and consume before drinking slow alcohol absorption.

Certain games are recommended for alcoholics such as swimming, basketball, and volleyball because such games have space for rest while playing the games.

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